

RHEOLOGY AND PACKING EFFECTS
IN THE INJECTION MOULDING OF
LONG FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The new class of long fibre reinforced thermoplastics enables products to be injection moulded with a much higher residual fibre length than was previously possible. Although these materials have a higher elongational viscosity than their short fibre counterparts, this quantity is not as high as might be expected, given their fibre length. Flow appears to involve movement of domains of oriented fibres, rather than individual dispersed entities. Clumps and bundles of oriented material can survive passage through the nozzle of a moulding to survive intact in the final product.

INTRODUCTION

There are several shaping operations in composite technology where bulk flow of discontinuous fibres in a liquid matrix occurs, the principal one at present being injection moulding. There is considerable benefit to be gained in such operations by maximising fibre length and volume fraction.

Until recently the fibre aspect ratios that could be preserved in injection moulding were limited to about 100 or less. This limitation corresponded quite well to the packing limitation of randomly oriented rods. Although the fibre orientation pattern observed in injection moulded products is far from random, it may be surmised that at some

point during the manufacturing sequence, probably at the compounding stage, a random orientation is imposed on the fibres.

The packing behaviour of randomly oriented rods has been investigated by Milewski [1], who showed that there was a well-defined relationship between the aspect ratio, L/d , of the rods and the maximum achievable packing fraction, V . In the concentration region of interest, it has been shown [2] that this relationship has the form:

$$L/d = k/V \quad \{1\}$$

where k is a constant with a value in the range 4-6.

In a process such as extrusion compounding where both fibres and matrix are subjected to mixing and shear in the barrel of an extruder, the final fibre aspect ratio is normally less than or equal to the value predicted by equation {1}, regardless of the initial value of L/d . A number of workers, for instance Von Turkovich and Erwin [3], have measured fibre length distribution at various points in the compounding process and have shown that most of the fibre breakage takes place during the initial fibre wet-out. Subsequent processing such as repeated extrusion or injection moulding has little further effect.

Although there is scope for improving the extrusion compounding process, for instance by melting the resin before adding the fibres, the limitation imposed by equation {1} is likely to remain for this type of process.

Until recently, relatively little attention had been paid to the possibility of increasing volume fraction or fibre length by processing discontinuous fibre composites with other than random initial orientation. It was assumed that the reorienting effect of flow through the barrel of an injection moulding machine would introduce random orientation and render the material liable to fibre breakage. However, nylon and polypropylene moulding materials are now available containing 50% by weight of well-impregnated parallel fibres, 10mm in length [4]. Surprisingly, these materials can be injection moulded with relative ease and little fibre breakage [5].

This paper will compare the rheological properties of the new long fibre (LF) nylon 66 moulding materials with those of conventional short fibre (SF) compounds and unfilled (UF) polymer. The reasons for the processability of LF materials, and their resistance to fibre degradation will be discussed.

PACKING EFFECTS WITH DIFFERENT TYPES OF FIBRE ORIENTATION

The relationship between volume fraction and aspect ratio is shown in figure 1 for three different types of fibre orientation: unidirectional, random in plane and three-dimensionally random. Only in the unidirectional case is the achievable packing fraction independent of the fibre aspect ratio. It can be seen that the LF materials considerably exceed the bounds for both random 3-D and random in plane orientation. It appears that in this material, neighbouring fibres remain approximately parallel, despite the large flow deformations imposed during processing. The effective aspect ratio during flow must be that of the flowing domains of approximately parallel fibres, rather than of individual fibres. The fact that fibres are locally parallel may also explain the low levels of fibre degradation, since each fibre is separated from its neighbour by a protective lubricating film of polymer.

FLOW BEHAVIOUR OF MOULDING MATERIALS

Capillary rheometer measurements were made at high shear rate values, typical of those encountered in injection moulding, on the moulding materials at a nominal temperature of 285C. An instrumented injection moulding machine was used for this, as described in previous publications [6,7]. The pressure drops for LF, SF and UF materials through dies of different length are shown in figure 2 for a shear rate of 5000 sec⁻¹. While all three materials show a significant die entry pressure drop, the LF material has by far the highest, implying that it has a high resistance to extensional flow, i.e. a high extensional viscosity. Similar large entrance effects have been observed previously with dough moulding compounds [6,7] and in polypropylene [8,9,10].

In simple fluids, the extensional viscosity is three times the shear viscosity. Unfilled polymer melts generally conform to this at very low deformation rates, where molecular orientation and viscoelastic effects are minimal. At processing strainrates, however, particularly when convergent flow is involved, there can be considerable molecular alignment, leading to extensional viscosities many times higher than three times the shear viscosity. In addition to molecular orientation, fibre alignment in reinforced compounds can also produce an increase in extensional viscosity, the two effects often occurring simultaneously.

The entry effects for the UF and SF materials are rather smaller with the present material, nylon 66, than in previous

measurements on polypropylene [8]. This may be because the nylon melt is closer to being an ideal fluid than polypropylene and also because the fibre aspect ratio in nylon SF compounds is somewhat lower than in polypropylene. Although the entry effect for the LF material is much higher than that for the SF, the value is not high enough to represent a barrier to processability and the increase is less than might have been expected, given the considerable difference in fibre length between the materials.

The mechanics of shear flow in capillaries is well-understood and documented, but the same is not yet true of die entry flow, where relationships between pressure drop and fluid properties are not as rigorous or well-tryed. However, many of the equations which have been proposed take the following general form:

$$P = P_{\text{Shear}} + P_{\text{Extension}} \quad \{2\}$$

$$\text{where } P_{\text{Shear}} = \eta \dot{\gamma} F(\theta) \left[1 - r_1^3 / r_0^3 \right] \quad \{3\}$$

$$\text{and } P_{\text{Extension}} = \lambda \dot{\gamma} G(\theta) \left[1 - r_1^3 / r_0^3 \right] \quad \{4\}$$

$F(\theta)$ and $G(\theta)$ are functions of the die semi-angle, r_0 and r_1 are the die entry and exit radii and $\dot{\gamma}$ is the wall shear rate at the die exit, given by $\dot{\gamma} = \frac{4Q}{\pi r_1^3}$.

The entry pressure consists of components arising from shear flow and from extensional flow. The shear flow contribution approaches infinity at zero die angle but decreases very rapidly with increasing die angle. In contrast the extensional flow component is zero at zero die angle and increases with increasing die angle. The relationship proposed by Cogswell [11] is probably the best known of this type, but will not be used here because it is not accurate at large die semi-angles. Instead, a relationship will be used which is derived assuming the velocity field proposed by Oka [12]. This derivation [13] gives:

$$F(\theta) = \frac{\sin\theta \cos\theta (1 + \cos\theta)^2}{4(1 - \cos\theta)(2\cos\theta + 1)} \quad \{5\}$$

and

$$G(\theta) = \frac{\sin\theta (1 + \cos\theta)}{6} + \frac{3 \left[\ln \left[\frac{2(1 - \cos\theta)}{\sin^2\theta} \right] \right]^2}{4(2 - 3\cos\theta + \cos^3\theta)} \quad \{6\}$$

The shear viscosity can be calculated from the capillary pressure drop using the Hagen-Poiseuille equation, so the magnitude of the shear contribution to the die entry pressure can be found from equation {3}. The extensional viscosity can then be found using equation {4}.

Figure 3 shows extensional and shear viscosities for all three types of compound, calculated by this procedure. The ratios of extensional to shear viscosity are all considerably higher than three: more than 10 for the UF and SF materials, and more than 100 for the LF. The other feature is that, the variation in extensional viscosity between the different materials is larger than the variation of shear viscosity. The similarity in shear viscosities is probably due to the high level of fibre alignment in the flow direction. When shear occurs parallel to the fibres they will be least effective in raising the viscosity and fibre length will have the lowest effect.

Batchelor [14] derived the following equation for the extensional viscosity of a fluid containing aligned fibres:

$$\lambda = \eta_{\text{Res}} \left[3 + \frac{4v(L/d)^2}{3 \ln(C/v)} \right] \quad \{7\}$$

where η_{Res} is the shear viscosity of the fluid.

Gibson and Lamb [15] showed that this equation, with values of the constant, C, in the range 0.907-3.628 could be applied to the fairly concentrated suspensions often encountered in polymer processing. Although {7} applies strictly to a Newtonian fluid, it can be modified to allow for the case where the fluid itself has a high extensional viscosity:

$$\lambda = \lambda_{\text{Res}} + \frac{4}{3} \eta_{\text{Res}} v \frac{(L/d)^2}{\ln(C/v)} \quad \{8\}$$

where λ_{Res} is the extensional viscosity of the resin.

Since the unfilled resin viscosity parameters are known, the effective L/d of the reinforcement in extensional flow can be calculated for both the SF and LF resins from this equation. For the SF material at 5000 s⁻¹, L/d lies in the region 10 -15 depending on the value chosen for C above. This is of the same order as the expected aspect ratio of the fibres, so it can be concluded that the fibres flow as a dispersion of individual entities. With the LF material, however, the calculated aspect ratio is 48-72. This is

considerably lower than the actual fibre aspect ratio, which, even allowing for some fibre breakage, must be in the region of 200-600. This is further evidence that LF materials flow as agglomerations of parallel fibres, rather than dispersed entities. Given the squared L/d term in equation {8}, the extensional viscosity of LF compounds would be impossibly high if the fibres did flow as dispersed entities.

To study the effect of die entry angle on flow behaviour, measurements were made of the entry pressure with dies having semi-angles in the range 7.5-90 degrees. A convenient way of representing die entry pressure data is to convert the pressure to a dimensionless quantity by dividing by exit shear rate and viscosity. This dimensionless measure of the entry effect can be shown to be equal to twice the intercept on the $1/r$ axis of the plots shown in figure 2 (the Bagley ends number).

Figure 4 shows values of the dimensionless entry effect as a function of die angle for the three compounds. The curves, particularly the one for the UF compound, show remarkably little variation with die angle at higher die angles. The solid lines were calculated from equations {3-5}. The values of the ratio of extensional to shear viscosity which gave the best fit were 345, 30 and 9 respectively for the LF, SF and UF cases. Although there is some deviation of the experimental points from the curve, the general correspondence between theory and results is encouraging.

FIBRE ORIENTATION DURING FLOW AND IN MOULDINGS

Figure 5 is a micro-radiograph of a section through an LF plaque moulding which clearly shows the presence of surface layers oriented in the mould flow direction. Similar layers are well-known in SF mouldings. In the centre of the plaque, however, there is a thick core containing macroscopically inhomogeneous swirls and bundles of long fibres. This is different to the case of SF mouldings, where the central core is generally much thinner and contains more homogeneously dispersed fibres. Figure 6, which is a section through the flow front of a short moulding shot, shows that the central core of the flowing material contains large, inhomogeneous swirls of long fibres oriented in various directions. The shear flow field has a strong orienting effect on the material near to the mould wall. Many of those fibre bundles which have their main axes approximately transverse to the flow direction and their ends near to one of the mould surfaces are pulled out of the core and go to form part of the aligned skin.

Figure 7, which is a section through the sprue of a moulding shows that, even in this region of most severe shear, following the intense elongational deformation in the nozzle, there are inhomogeneously-dispersed swirls of material, few of which are oriented parallel to the flow direction. It was decided to examine the flow field within the die to discover why this material had failed to become completely oriented. The technique used involved stopping the machine during a capillary flow experiment and freezing off material in the die. Accepting that some movement, contraction and distortion can take place during freezing it was still felt that this would give a useful insight into the flow pattern.

Figure 8 shows polished cross-sections of samples obtained from two freezing off experiments with LF material using a 45 degree die. In the first photograph, 1% of a carbon fibre LF compound was added as a tracer. This sample shows striations corresponding to an approximately parabolic flow profile well upstream from the die. On approaching the die, this profile becomes distorted and there is evidence of two zones of flow: an outer region of oriented material which may be slow-moving or stagnant, and an inner region containing disordered bundles and swirls. In order to determine the relative velocities of these two zones, a further solidification experiment was performed involving a change from the compound containing the carbon marker to one without the marker and back again. The flow pattern suggests that the outer oriented layer is slow moving, but not stagnant. Further solidification experiments [16] revealed the presence of a slow-moving outer layer even at die angles as low as 7.5 degrees.

The presence of disordered bundles and swirls is evidence of a departure from homogeneous flow, just upstream from the die. The fibre bundles near to the flow axis at the leading edge of the distorted parabolic velocity profile will be oriented in several directions, all of which are perpendicular to the flow axis. Under the influence of the extensional flow field at the die entrance these differently oriented bundles flow inhomogeneously, sliding over one another and becoming progressively bent and distorted as they reach the die exit. This bending and distortion does not produce much orientation in the flow direction, but does store significant elastic energy by bending of the fibres. Release of this energy after passage through the die results in the phenomenon of "fibre foaming", where the extrudate expands considerably to form a porous woolly network of fibres. This has been described previously with LF polymers [5], and, followed by a subsequent coining process has been suggested as a forming technique for these materials. Fibre foaming is also well-known with materials such as DMC in the thermoset industry, where it is regarded as evidence of fibre length retention. It is interesting to note in connection

with the present work that conventional SF thermoplastic moulding materials show very little die swell- in keeping with their much shorter fibre length.

It seems probable therefore that the thick swirling core of mouldings in LF compounds results from this inhomogeneous flow at the die entry. This does not imply necessarily that LF mouldings have inferior properties. Indeed in several situations these materials have been shown to have many advantages over their SF counterparts.

CONCLUSIONS

Long fibre thermoplastic moulding materials containing parallel well-wetted fibres can be readily processed by injection moulding without undue fibre breakage. These materials exhibit a high extensional viscosity in convergent flow, but not as high a value as might have been expected, given their large aspect ratio. Flow of these materials involves movement of domains of parallel fibres, rather than flow of fibres as individual entities. There is evidence of inhomogeneous flow in the die entry.

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REFERENCES

1. Milewski, J. V., "Handbook of fillers and reinforcements for plastics", Van Nostrand Reinhold, 1978.
2. Evans, K. E. and Gibson, A. G., Composites Science and Technology, 25, 1, 1986.
3. Von Turkovich, R. and Erwin, L., Polymer Engineering Science, 23, 13, 743, 1983.
4. Product data on "Verton" long fibre reinforcement, ICI Petrochemicals and Plastics Division, Wilton, Cleveland, UK.
5. Cuff, G., paper 19, British Plastics Federation 14th Reinforced Plastics Congress, Brighton, November, 1984.
6. Williamson, G. A. and Gibson, A. G., Plastics and Rubber Processing and Applications, 4, 3, 203, 1984.

7. Gibson, A. G. and Williamson, G. A., Polymer Engineering Science, 25, 968, 1985.
8. Crowson, R. J., Scott, A. J. and Saunders, D. W., Polymer Engineering Science, 21, 748, 1981.
9. Gibson, A. G., McClelland, A. N., Cuff, G. and Gore, C. R., page 511, Proceedings of the 1st ECCM conference, Bordeaux, France, September 1985.
10. Gibson, A. G. and McClelland, A. N., page 99, Proceedings of the conference on Fibre Reinforced Composites, University of Liverpool, I. Mech. E., April 1986.
11. Cogswell, F. N., Polymer Engineering Science, 12, 64, 1972.
12. Oka, S., J. of the Phys. Soc. of Japan, 19, 8, 1481, 1964.
13. Gibson, A. G., in preparation.
14. Batchelor, G. K., J. of Fluid Mechanics, 46, 813, 1971.
15. Lamb, D. W., Ph.D. Thesis, University of Liverpool, 1985.
16. Gibson, A. G. and McClelland, A. N., in preparation.

Figure 1. Relationship between maximum volume fraction and fibre aspect ratio for three different types of fibre orientation.

Figure 2. Plots of die entry pressure vs. die length, at an exit shear rate of 5000 s^{-1} , for LF, SF and UF nylon materials. Die semi-angle, 45 degrees. Die bore diameter, 4mm.

Figure 3. Shear and extensional viscosity data vs. strain rate for LF, SF and UF nylons.

Figure 4. Dimensionless entry pressure vs. die angle, at an exit shear rate of 5000 s^{-1} , for LF, SF and UF nylons.

Figure 5. Radiograph of a section through a 4mm thick LF nylon plaque, perpendicular to the mould flow direction.

Figure 6. Radiograph showing a section through the flow front of a short shot LF nylon moulding.

Figure 7. Section through the sprue of a LF nylon moulding.

Figure 8. Photographs of polished sections through solidified slugs of LF nylon. (a) Material containing 1% of LF carbon fibre tracer. (b) As above, after two material changes, showing slow-moving zones.